

“SÉRIES ESTUDOS” MAGAZINE: A FRAMEWORK IN HUMANIST TEACHER TRAINING AT INTEGRATED SCHOOLS SANTO TOMÁS DE AQUINO, UBERABA/MG

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ABSTRACT

When investigating the concepts and practices experienced at Faculties Integrates Santo Tomás de Aquino - FISTA, Uberaba/MG, in the 60's and 80's, period of its consolidation in the field of the history of school institutions in higher education, we came across productions related to teacher training humanist. By reinterpreting the autobiographical accounts, we understand that the anthropological conception of curriculum tended to humanize the relationships between subjects. We analyzed the periodical “Series Studies” as a source of research on the existing power relations within the institution. We opted for the phenomenological and hermeneutic method of bibliographic analysis in which the testimonies and references turn to cultural history, according to Roger Chartier, to Bourdieu's sociology, to the so-called post-structuralist current. The analysis of the periodical made it possible to resize the training experiences, educational practices and institutional memories.

Keywords: Studies Series, FISTA, humanist teacher training.

INTRODUCTION

The memory and university teaching training of Faculdades Integradas Santo Tomás de Aquino (1949-1980), FISTA, from Uberaba, Minas Gerais, created and administered by the Congregation of the Dominican Sisters Nossa Senhora do Rosário de Monteils, reveal a concern with the construction of knowledge and knowledge based on an intellectual thought open to research, to diversity, rooted in principles of Christian humanism. FISTA's teaching training was based on reflection on the causes and social consequences of class struggle, power relations and domination in the social space. The Dominican institution opened spaces for study groups, the creation of newspapers and magazines, extracurricular courses and controversial debates such as basic social, university and agrarian reforms. FISTA alumnus and professor Dr. Eduardo Roberto Junqueira Guimarães, currently advisor and member of the Rectorry of the

University of Campinas – UNICAMP – ensures that political training was part of the Brazilian scenario and Uberaba in the 60s and 70s:

I was president of the Academic Directory in 1967, I think until 1969. I took on several functions in the Directory, member responsible for the Communication sector and for the newspaper “O Coruja”. I was president of the Centro de Estudos de Português, a research center that integrated the area of Portuguese Literature. I was president of the Latin Academy which was a student institution related to the teaching of Latin. I was director of the Department of Literature and, at that time, I founded a publication called “Série Estudos”. (SANTOS, 05/30/2006).

2 - THEORETICAL FOUNDATION AND STUDY METHODOLOGY

2.1- A look at educational practices, ways to build a teaching identity

The memory and university teaching training of Faculdades Integradas Santo Tomás de Aquino reveal a concern with the construction of knowledge and knowledge based on an intellectual thought open to research, to diversity, rooted in principles of Christian humanism.

Antonio Nóvoa brings numerous reflections on the life and action of teachers. He appropriates his personal experience, his historically constructed knowledge, the search for knowledge and socializes, reflects, provokes a new organization of thought in the collective. NÓVOA's approach to the reflective teacher contributes to the characterization of the FISTA faculty who, based on the reports, demonstrated a relationship with demanding students, with academic rigor that began with the careful selection for admission to college. There was care with knowledge while knowledge under construction. Certain rigor of intellectual work with a requirement in intellectual production. The selection process was based on quality, the entrance exam failed, giving the teacher freedom of action, a requirement in monitoring and in the way of doing things: practical and reflective. NÓVOA draws attention to this important aspect in the training process:

“ In this way, to make history as knowledge and as experience is to recover the action of the different groups that act in it, trying to understand why the process took a given direction and not another; it means rescuing the injunctions that allowed the realization of one possibility and not others (NÓVOA 1992, p.22). □□

According to NÓVOA, teacher training is not built by accumulating courses, techniques or content. Training is only effective and will bear fruit if it is through reflective, analytical work on practices. A dynamic movement, a permanent exercise in the reconstruction of

personal identity, which presupposes an open relationship with knowledge. It values the pedagogical routine and discusses the importance that “life stories” can acquire in studies on teacher training.

In this line of thought, it can be seen that FISTA's teaching training was based on reflection on the causes and social consequences of class struggle, power relations and domination in the social space, in the fields: spaces of positions, struggles and disputes. It is known that there are specific laws for each field. To know them, it is necessary to understand the places where knowledge is produced: the institutions, the State, the agents and their relationships.

Education, teaching systems and pedagogical actions that take place within families and in school routine occupy a central place in the social theory and research of the French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu. Bourdieu's comprehensive sociological theory treats education as a fundamental component of the process of constituting the social world, elaborating some concepts such as *habitus*, practice, strategy, field, cultural capital, symbolic violence and social reproduction. Pierre Bourdieu presents us with a clear view of social representations: how each agent develops their forms of “ *perception, thought and action* ” through which the apprehension of the world is carried out and the orientation of practical conduct in day-to-day life and its relationships with other agents. Bourdieu defends the idea that social representations are influenced by ideas, values, beliefs and ideologies that previously existed in a society, and that are present in the language we use to communicate, in religions and in the so-called common sense that make up the *habitus* of each agent, and also the conceptions that circulate among the participants of the social fields, professional groups and social classes.

It is noticed that social representations have a historical, collective origin, because when we act and interact with other individuals we have the ability to formulate and reformulate our own representations and thus guide the particular points of view that we elaborate on reality and the practical decisions that we make. we adopted.

It is necessary to know the *habitus* as incorporated history: its time, its mode of existence. There is a specific mode of existence in each space , *habitus*. Saint Thomas Aquinas, in the Summa Theologica, translates it into Latin with the meaning of “durable suspended disposition”, located between “ *potency* ” and “ *purposeful action* ”. Bourdieu expands the concept by proposing it as a means of “ *breaking with the common sense duality between individual and society* ”, with the intention of capturing the “ *interiorization of exteriority and the exteriorization of interiority* ”. It was necessary to overcome subjectivism in society; having provisions for action: *habitus*: structured structures, able to function as structuring structures.

These are structuring aspects of reality, where the actions of agents are closely related to their socialization, which assumes an embodied form(s) through *habitus*, which are expressed in attitudes, tastes, opinions, skills, values and dispositions. How does the subject incorporate the outside world and make all of this his thinking and then start to intervene in reality? Under what conditions (who? How? And why?) did FISTA professors produce the journal “Série Estudos”?

The publication *Série Estudos* cited by Professor Dr. Eduardo Roberto Junqueira Guimarães was his initiative, in 1972, during his tenure as Director of the Department of Literature. This, created in 1965, recorded in its minutes the “ *need to work together to better integrate the different subjects and better use by the students* ”. Its creation aimed to value the studies and research of the Department's professors. The actions developed in the Department were essential for the creation and dissemination of the journal.

The first volume of the “ *Studies Series* ”, in 1972, with the theme “On Language and Literature” presented texts by professors of the Department of Literature, productions arising from courses, debates, research and discussions within the Faculty. Its life cycle from 1972 to 1986, totaling 12 volumes, became a national reference.

The testimonies of the creator of the magazine “Série Estudos” help us to reflect on these issues, when in the 60s, in the middle of the military dictatorship, FISTA committed itself to a differential: intellectual independence of the students. According to Dr. Eduardo Guimaraes:

[...] *There was a lot of this issue of students' independence, the need for students to dedicate themselves strongly to reading, researching and getting involved, including in assessment procedures. All undergraduate courses ended with a specific monograph, for each discipline of that period. It was a very strong requirement. (SANTOS, May 30, 2006)*

In 1977, Sr. Heloisa Seixas Leite, then director of the Department of Literature, presented the third volume of the *Series* that expanded the participation of other universities in the theme of language and valued the studies and research of FISTA professors, such as Eduardo Guimarães and Vânia Maria Resende.

In the following eleven volumes, the coordinator expands the participation of specialists from other Brazilian universities who disseminate research and studies relevant to the critical study of the language. They stand out: Francis H. Aubert (USP), Eni Orlandi (USP), Marta Steinberg (USP), Maria Beatriz Luti and Maria Bernardette de Oliveira (UFRN), Maria Stela Gonçalves (USP), Peter Fry and Eduardo Guimarães (UNICAMP).

Prof. doctor Eduardo Roberto Junqueira Guimarães began his Literature course at FISTA in 1966, with his training in linguistics being extremely structuralist. Another significant aspect arising from the testimony and performance of Eduardo Roberto Junqueira Guimarães refers to the “ *way of organization of youth* ”. There was leadership training at FISTA due to the high criteria for selecting students. The entrance exam itself was demanding, it selected a certain profile. With the presence of a qualified, well-trained faculty, it was possible to teach how to think, to take into account some values essential to human beings. In this perspective, the quoted professor added:

Every formative institution that succeeds in what it does, it stands in the prayers that it founded. [...] when I say teaching to do, I mean teaching to think, to analyze... It's not giving a concept, it means that. No, teach to do. Therefore, thinking, doing things, making decisions, describing, analyzing, interpreting... I think this is an important trait she had. And any good institution does. It is clear that she was somewhat affected by some particular trait. [...] maybe this is the trait that remains in many people. What people sometimes learned was not exactly this notion of humanism in the sense that man is the center of knowledge, man is the fundamental object of knowledge. But it's the notion that you have to take into account a value and then teach how to do it. In this sense, how you think, how you interpret things, how you analyze things, how you describe things, deal with people, do whatever it is (SANTOS, May 30, 2006).

This humanist trait gives the institution a consistent practice, an experience that allowed the student to have a firm line of thought, free from the catechetical aspect. There was freedom of thought, which gives FISTA a university character, a university in fact, of open intellectual thought that respected plurality.

3 - RESULTS ANALYSIS

Tables 01 and 02 present the main collaborators of the “Série Estudos”, from 1972 to 1986, with the number of articles published in each volume. It offers a broad view of each year and the period of its interruption (1973 to 1975), in view of Professor Eduardo Guimarães going to the Master's degree at USP. A “stop” that opened new paths and perspectives, giving greater visibility to the Magazine. Another interruption was in 1980, when FISTA was camped by FIUBE – Faculdades Integradas de Uberaba. From volume 07 onwards, the publication was entrusted to FIUBE, but with the same editorial coordination.

Table 01 - Main Collaborators of the "Study Series" - 1972 to 1980

Collaborators	1972 (n.1)	1973	1974	1975	1976 (n.2)	1977 (n.3)	1978 (n.4)	1978 (n. 5)	1979 (n.6)	1980
Eduardo Guimaraes	02	-	-	-	01	01	03	01	01	-
Evandro Silva Martins	02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Regina Stela Bessa	01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Marco Anton. escobar	01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Eni Pulcinelli Orlandi	-	-	-	-	01	02	03	01	01	-
Francis H. Aubert	-	-	-	-	02	01	03	01	-	-
Martha Steinberg	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-	-
Maria Beatriz Luti	-	-	-	--	01	01	-	-	-	-
Maria Bernadette F. de Oliveira	-	-	-	-	01	01	-	-	-	-
Maria Stela Gonçalves	-	-	-	-	01	01	-	01	-	-
Maria Helena Carrasqueira	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-	-
Maria Teresa da Silva Fonseca	-	-	--	-	01	-	-	-	-	-
Geraldine P. Witter	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-
Vânia Maria Resende	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-
Carlos Alberto da Fonseca	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-
Elsa Maria MP Pullin	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-
José Alves Zanatta	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-
Maria Helena R. Lopes	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-
Maria Thereza O.de Melo	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-

Sylvia Ignez D. Megda	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-	-	-
Herman Parret	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-
João Wanderley Geraldi	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mara Cristina Queiroz Franco	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	01	-	-
Syrian Possenti	-	-	-	-	-	--	-	-	01	-
Haqira Osakabe	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	01	-
Antonio Alcir Pécora	-	--	-	-	-	-	-	-	01	--
Maria Cecília Perroni Simões	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	01	--

Table 02 – Main Collaborators of the “Studies Series” - 1981 to 1986

Collaborators	1981 (n.7)	1982 (n.8)	1983 (n.9)	1984 (n.10)	1985 (n.11)	1986 (n.12)	TOTAL
Eduardo Guimaraes	01	-	01	-	01	01	04
Eni Pulcinelli Orlandi	01	--	01	-	-	01	05
Maria Cecília Perroni Simões	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Marco Ant. Oliveira	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Mario A. Perini	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Rodolfo Ilari	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Norma Hochgreb	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Daisi Rocha B. Pazzaglini	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Eloisa C. Lenzi	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Maria Margarida de Andrade	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Maria Del Pilar S. Martin	01	-	-	-	-	-	01
Goodbye Marta Ide	01	-	-	-	-	-	01

Mary Aizawa Kato	-	02	01	-	-	-	03
Luiz Antonio Marcushi	-	01	-	-	-	-	01
Lucia Kopschitz Xavier Bastos	-	01	-	-	-	-	01
Luiz Carlos Cagliari	-	01	-	-	-	-	01
Iara Bemquerer Costa	-	01	-	-	-	-	01
Leila Barbara	-	01	-	-	-	-	01
Carlos Vogt	-	-	01	-	-	01	02
Kanavillil Rajagopalan	-	-	02	-	-	-	02
Ingedore Grunfeld Villaça Koch	-	-	01	-	-	01	02
Carlos Alberto Faraco	-	-	01	-	-	-	01
Claudia TG de Lemos	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Eleonora A. da Motta Maia	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
José Borges Neto	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Celia Regina Carneiro from Toledo	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Maria Francisca AF Lier	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Ester Miriam Scarpa	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Nina Virgínia de A. Leite	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Fernando Taralho	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Maria Luiza Braga	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Maria Cecília Magalhães Mollica	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Leonor Lopes Favero	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Ingedore G. Villaça	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Silvana Serrani	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
peter fry	-	-	-	-	-	01	01
Tânia Conceicao Clemente de Souza	-	-	-	-	-	01	01

The *Studies Series* brought a qualitative leap in the history of teacher training at FISTA and was a reference for many universities. As well as the Centro de Estudos which had a library of Portuguese Literature donated by the Carlos Bolbec Foundation. The courses of Contemporary Portuguese Poetry, of great repercussion, had the presence of Prof. Fernando Manuel de Mendonça from the University of Assis.

Table 03 lists the names of the members of the Editorial Board, the period they were on the Editorial Board and the number of articles published. It is noticed that there is a close relationship between these numbers based on the context of work, personal relationships, approaches in the line of research and study groups. There is an opening to other universities as Editorial Board Director Dr. Eduardo Guimarães is studying at the USP Master's and Doctorate, opening up new possibilities for interaction and deepening of the themes. The main coordinators of the *Série Estudos* : Eduardo Roberto Guimarães and Eni Orlandi have a very close training trajectory.

Table 03- Editorial Board

members	Time spent on the Board	Number of articles published
Eduardo Roberto Junqueira Guimaraes	1972 to 1986	12
Eni Pulcinelli Orlandi	1976 to 1986	11
Claudia TG de Lemos	1985	01
Carlos Vogt	1983 to 1986	02

The Table 04 summarizes the themes of publications, year by year, in each of the 12 volumes with the number of articles in each one. An interesting detail is the balance in the number of articles published in each volume and the possibility of interlocution between them. The authors who published the most throughout the life cycle of the Journal were: Eduardo Guimarães, 12 articles; Eni Pulcinelli Orlandi, 11 articles and Francis Henrik Aubert, 08.

Table 04 - Theme of publications

Year	Thematic	number of articles	Volume
1972	About language and literature	06	01
1976	Linguistic Studies	06	02
1977	About Language	08	03
1978	Focus and Assumption	03	04
1978	About Semantics	07	05
1979	About the Speech	06	06
1981	Portuguese: Linguistic Studies	07	07
1982	Written and Oral Languages	06	08
1983	About Pragmatics	08	09
1984	Linguistics: Issues and Controversies	08	10
1985	Language Acquisition	07	11
1986	The Historical and the Discursive	08	12

4 - FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In view of the reflections made, it is concluded that the periodical “Série Estudos”, with a relatively short life cycle, with 12 volumes, marked the history of teacher training at FISTA. The meticulous analysis of the journal “merged” with the reports of managers and collaborators, in an autobiographical perspective, allowed the resizing of the training experiences, the teaching trajectory, the educational practices, their institutional memories, intellectual and affective memories. The journal's guiding axis is the construction of knowledge, knowledge, in a critical, reflexive, questioning way, with rigor and care; Combining language and discourse with the dimensions of “ *learning to be* ” and “ *learning to do* ”: a humanistic teacher education.

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